

ISSN P-0972-3331 | E-2582-8711

jnanadeepa

Pune Journal of Religious Studies

The Constitutive Other The Other as Part of Us

Volume 25/3

July 2021

Jnana Deepa, Pune, India

www.jdv.edu.in

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4459906

Stable URL: [doi.org/ DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4459906](https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4459906)

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ISSN: P-0972-3331

CODEN: JNANAR

OCLC: 39746721

IXTHEO: 246049707

LCCN: 98903113

VIAF ID: 151453884

www.punejournal.in

Jnanadeepa (= "Light of Wisdom" pronounced as *Gyanadeepa*) is a peer-reviewed interdisciplinary quarterly journal of religious studies from Indian Christian perspectives. It is closely associated with Jnana Deepa, Institute of Philosophy and Theology, Pune 411 014, India.

Jnanadeepa is published in January, April, July and October. Views expressed by the writers are not necessarily endorsed by the editors. Manuscripts submitted for publication should be original and cannot be returned (writers' style sheet is available on request); they could be sent (preferably as RTF and PDF files) as E-mail attachments.

All **correspondence** (requests for subscriptions, manuscripts, books for review-two copies, please exchange copies of journals, advertisements, etc.) to:

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Subscriptions could be sent from India online. From foreign countries International Money Order or Crossed Cheque is preferred. From Commonwealth countries British Postal Order is preferred. All payments (Cheque, drafts, etc. are to be made in the name of *Jnana Deepa*.

Printed at: Kunal Offset, 412, Kakasaheb Gadgil Rd, Shaniwar Peth, Pune, Maharashtra 411030 Mob: 098230 48871

Subscription Rates

Country	One Year	Three Years
India	₹ 250	₹ 600
SAARC Countries	₹ 300	₹ 750
Other Countries (Air Mail)	\$ 25 (€ 25)	\$ 55 (€ 55)
Institutional Rate	\$ 50 (€ 45)	\$ 110 (€ 110)

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Editorial - The Constitutive Other: The Other as Part of Us

We tend to see the other as opposed to ourselves or as rivals. Sometimes we even treat them as our enemies. At the same time, the challenge we face in our pluralistic and diverse world is to befriend the other, recognise the otherness in the other with respect and compassion.

In phenomenology, the terms the Other and the Constitutive Other identify the other human being, in their differences from the Self, as being a cumulative, constituting factor in the self-image of a person; as acknowledgement of being real; hence, the Other is dissimilar to and the opposite of the Self, of Us, and of the Same. The Constitutive Other is the relation between the personality (essential nature) and the person (body) of a human being; the relation of essential and superficial characteristics of personal identity that corresponds to the relationship between opposite, but correlative, characteristics of the Self, because the difference is inner-difference, within the Self (Wikipedia contributors, 2021).

The condition and quality of Otherness (the characteristics of the Other) is the state of being different from and alien to the social identity of a person and to the identity of the Self. In the discourse of philosophy, the term Otherness identifies and refers to the characteristics of Who? and What? of the Other, which are distinct and separate from the Symbolic order of things; from the Real (the authentic and unchangeable); from the aesthetic (art, beauty, taste); from political philosophy; from social norms and social identity; and from the Self. Therefore, the condition of Otherness is a person's non-conformity to and with the social norms of society; and Otherness is the condition

Cite as: Pandikattu, Kuruvilla. (2021) The Constitutive Other (Version 1.0). Jnanadeepa: Pune Journal of Religious Studies, July 2021(Vol 25/3), 5-7. <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4459880>

of disenfranchisement (political exclusion), effected either by the State or by the social institutions invested with the corresponding socio-political power. Therefore, the imposition of Otherness alienates the person labelled as “the Other” from the centre of society, and places him or her at the margins of society, for being the Other.

The term Othering describes the reductive action of labelling and defining a person as a subaltern native, as someone who belongs to the socially subordinate category of the Other. The practice of Othering excludes persons who do not fit the norm of the social group, which is a version of the Self; likewise, in human geography, the practice of othering persons means to exclude and displace them from the social group to the margins of society, where mainstream social norms do not apply to them, for being the Other.

In the very provocative book, *Oneself as Another* (Ricoeur, 2008), the French existentialist Paul Ricoeur provides a stimulating examination of the role of personal identity and presents a brilliant insight into Ricoeur’s own views on subjectivity and the hermeneutics of the self.

According to Ricoeur, selfhood, far from referring to something concrete, discrete and fully understood, implies otherness to an unacknowledged degree. To speak of “the self” implies a relationship between the same and the other which the Cartesian cogito (“I think, therefore I am”) does not include. Unlike the cogito, which functions as a statement of knowledge, the hermeneutics of the self can only lead to an attestation of truth. However, Paul Ricoeur claims that such an attestation of belief is not inferior to knowledge, but merely expresses a different type of certainty (Greenaway, 1986).

The attesting of belief is a form of testimony, whereby the individual self, a verbal sign and assurance that the self believes in the truth of what it claims. From this defense of attestation Ricoeur moves on to discuss the dialectic relationship between selfhood and sameness. Sameness denotes a numerical identity, a qualitative identity or it may also denote an uninterrupted continuity. Selfhood, on the other hand, refers to the identity which belongs to one self and not another, or, more interestingly, one self as another.

According to Ricoeur our narrative identity is defined by the complex interplay between sameness and selfhood. The identity of an individual within a narrative is their narrative identity and to be in

possession of such an identity implies a capacity for action. Furthermore, a character in a narrative is an individual who may be re-identified as being the same. This becomes more complex as Ricoeur moves on to his discussion of responsibility. For a self to be responsible, it must be the same self which is believed to be the acting agent in any given situation, but still capable of change. Ricoeur singularly manages to turn the self into the self as other with the deliberate aim of provoking a new ethical awareness. Personal identity is inseparable from ethics (the aims of our personal behaviour) and morals (how this behaviour is carried out in the social realm.)

Ricoeur's careful untangling of the self allows the reader to see how conception of selfhood materially impact how we treat others (Greenaway, n.d.). Understanding oneself as another involves treating the Other when encountered in the world with empathy and respect – a new “solicitude” rather than any kind of moral solipsism whereby not only can we see ourselves as another, but we can also see the other as ourselves.

In this sense, we do have a collective responsibility for the other. To protect and promote the others (in their otherness) is our sacred responsibility. In view of these developments Jnana Deepa, Institute of Philosophy and Theology, Pune, organised an international Conference on Befriending the Other on November 24-28, 2015. Some of the papers were published in 2016 issue of *Jnanadeepa* (Vol 20/1-2) The papers in this volume are revised presentations of that Conference, which attempts to acknowledge, respect and befriend the other.

The Editor

Referenece

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